

The feeding behavior of Spined-soldier bug (*Eocanthecona furcellata* Wolff.) on caterpillar of Common banded awl (*Harsora chromus*) in kota, Rajasthan.

Sonu Kumar*

*District coordinator kota at Biodiversity research and development society
India.

More than half of the organisms found on earth are insect species, which are found all over the world. Here I am talking about an insect species, which can be easily seen in the trees, gardens and wild and agricultural landscapes around us. These insects are colloquially called bedbugs and are known all over the world as Spined-soldier bugs. It is a member of the Hemiptera order of the insect class. The Spined-soldier bug is named after the two spiny projections present on either side of its thorax. Spined-soldier bugs are a predatory insect species that prey on other insects, hence they are also called biological pest controllers as they prey mostly on insects that harm crops such as moths, butterflies and beetle caterpillars.

I have mostly seen them eating caterpillars on Karanja tree. On finding out the relationship of the caterpillars found on Karanja trees, it was found that their relationship is of parasitism, here one organism gets benefit (+) and the other organism gets harm (-). These caterpillars belong to a butterfly called Common Banded Awl and Karanja tree is the host plant of the caterpillar of this butterfly, that is, the caterpillars survive by eating the leaves of Karanja tree. But sometimes when the number of caterpillars increases, they also harm the tree. Therefore, due to the good number of caterpillars on the leaves of the tree, these Spined-soldier bugs do not have much difficulty in finding prey. Spined-soldier bugs play an important role in controlling the population of caterpillars present on Karanja tree by eating them, that is why these Spined-soldier bugs are also considered as biological pest controllers.

The process of hunting and eating the caterpillars:

The Spined Soldier Bug has adapted itself to its environment in such a way that it can easily hunt its prey without becoming prey to other predators. These predatory Spined-soldier bugs have some special structures in their body which provide them protection from other predatory creatures and also help in catching prey. These insects

have a shield-like rough armor on their body in which two thorn-like projections are found and two long antennae between which a long snout protrudes forward from the mouth, which is called beak/proboscis. Their beak is thicker than the antennae, flat, pipe-like and straight, which is mobile and sharp from the front, which works to kill the prey and suck its juice. Under normal circumstances the beak is not visible because it remains stuck to the lower surface of the body. But when the bed bug comes near one of its prey or caterpillars, it takes out its beak and attacks it swiftly. Due to the sharp beak, it easily penetrates the body of the prey/caterpillar. Now through its beak it secretes some digestive juice inside its prey, which paralyzes the prey and also starts digesting its internal parts. After this, it slowly sucks the digested internal parts with the help of beak and keeps taking nutrition. This strategy of these hunting insects sometimes proves to be so effective that they capture prey many times larger than their

Figure: A: Adult *Eocanthecona furcellata* Wolff. B,C&D: *Eocanthecona furcellata* Wolff predated a common banded awl caterpillar on a Pongam oil tree in outer road side.

own size.

References:

- Ambrose D P. 2006. A checklist of Indian assassin bugs (Insecta: Hemiptera: Reduviidae) with taxonomic status, distributio and diagnostic morphological characteristics. *Zoos' Print Journal* 21: 2388-2406.
- Aruna A S and Devi A R. 2015. Biology of a predatory bug *E. furcellata* Wolff (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) on Vapourer Tussock moth larvae: a major pest of tasar silkworm food plants. *International Journal of Industrial Entomology* 30(1): 26-30.
- Pandey, S.; Joshi, B.D.; Tiwari, L.D. 2005: New record of *Eocanthecona furcellata* (Wolff.), as a predator of the introduced Parthenium bio-control agent, *Zygogramma bichlorata* (Pallister) and its cannibalistic feeding behaviour *Entomon* 30(4): 347-349
- Rani, P.; Usha.; Havukkala, I. 1993: Predatory and mating behaviour of *Eocanthecona furcellata* (Wolff.) (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) a promising natural enemy of lepidopterous larvae *Journal of Biological Control* 7(1): 9-11
- Siddaiah A and Devi A R. 2015. Biology of a predatory bug *Eocanthecona furcellata* Wolff (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) on Vapourer tussock moth larvae: a major pest of tasar silkworm food plants. *International Journal of Industrial Entomology* 30(1): 26-30.
- Vineet kumar MN, Morrison S, Rajadurai AM, Babu V, Thiyagarajan Datta RK. Studies on the biology and Predatory ability of *Eocanthecona furcellata* (Wolff.) Predating on *Spilarctica oblique* (Walk.) in mulberry Plantation. *Int. J Indust Entomol.* 2001; 2(2):173-180.